

FEATURES OF FORMING DIGITAL COMPETENCES OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7438510>

Abstract: *The development of modern society, expressed in the general digitalization of all spheres of human life, includes a change in the educational landscape, which consists in transferring many types of educational activities to the global Internet. Given the emerging social conditions, a modern competitive specialist should have a certain level of digital competency. An analysis of the work in the field of digital competence showed that this concept is poorly understood.*

Keywords: *education, bachelor's degree, bachelor's training, higher education, digitalization of society, digital competence, the formation of digital competence, personal learning environment.*

Statement of the problem in general terms and its connection with the importance scientific and practical problems.

In the modern world, when rapid evolution information technology leads to changes in

economy, education, business, society; when fakthere is a fusion of technologies and services

the global Internet with daily life,are new concepts needed to comprehend.

General digitalization of most spheres of life quality becomes an impetus for the development of new thorns of behavior in the digital

space and in connection with this transforms the concept of "information-communication competence" to the concept of "digital competence".

Until recently, it was widely used the concept of "information and communication competence". Information researchers communicative competence, give different

definitions of this concept. Some authors believe that the meaning of this term is based on the technical component and is the ability to apply technical skills means for searching, storing and processing information in any activity of the subject (A.A. Elizarov [1], A.B. Bogdanov [2]). Another approach to defining information and communication competence

focused on the terms "information" and "communication" and the perception of in-

formations by the subject through communication, directed not on actions with information in professional and practical activities (A.M. Semibratov [3], V.F. Burmakin [4], A.A. Temerbekov [5], E.G. Drunk [6]). The aim of the program is to organize system development and implementation of digital technologies in all areas of life. Services are the backbone of the digital economy global network Internet. In this regard, one of

competencies that need to be developed for a new generation professional, is "digital competence". The question arises of the difference between the concepts "information and communication competence" and "digital competence".

Knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility as components digital competence in the listed areas .

They divide digital competence into four subspecies:

1) information and media competence - significant knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility associated with search, understanding, organization of digital information

information using digital resources and its critical logical comprehension;

2) communicative competence - knowledge, ability, motivation and responsibility necessary for various forms of communication (e-mail, chats, blogs, forums, social networks, etc.);

3) technical competence - knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibility to effectively

and safely use technical and software means for solving various problems, including the use of computer networks, cloud services and etc.;

4) consumer competence - knowledge, ability, motivation

and responsibility, allowing to solve using digital devices and the internet everyday tasks related to specific life

nennymi situations, suggesting the satisfaction different needs [8].

N.P. Yachin and G.G. Fernandez believe that in the concept "digital competence" includes "confident and critical student use of the computer, and mobile phone, tablet computer, internet active board. This competence is based on the logic logical thinking, a high level of management proficiency I eat information and highly developed mastery. digital technology" [9]. Into digital competence they propose to include: an understanding of the overall structure and interaction of computer devices; understanding of the potential digital technologies for innovative activities news; basic understanding of reliability and validity

the information received, the ability to use the software mami for designing a training session [9].

Issues of digital competence and digital literacy is also dealt with by the Regional Society

private organization "Center for Internet Technologies"(ROCIT). The website of this organization annual measurement of digital literacy levels and digital competence of citizens through testing roving. ROCIT

believes that "digital competencies are the skills to use technology effectively, including:

- search for information,
- use of digital devices,
- use of social networking functionality,
- financial operations,
- online shopping,
- critical perception of information,
- production of multimedia content,
- device synchronization" [10].

The European Commission, in its definition of digital howling competence (digital competency), prepared nom under the Action Plan for the Development of Digital education (DEAP), emphasizes the importance of awareness sustainable and responsible use of digital technology in education, at work and in social life.

Digital competence should include a way responsiveness to digital cooperation, security danger and problem solving [11].

Among the necessary skills for the success of an independent Simo from the specifics of the activity distinguish soft skills (English - "soft skills"), i.e. social and hard skills

(English - "solid skills"), - professional. But, in links with total computerization and digitalization in recent years, a new group of skills has

been identified, applicable to any specialists in the digital economy - digital skills (eng. - "digital skills ki").

Moreover, the skills of using digital technology logic should be based on a clear understanding of its meaning, awareness of the purpose of its use, and, most importantly,

noe, critical evaluation of the result, understanding what problems it might lead to. For example, critical selection of information for placement in social networks, careful financial

online operations, understanding that the Internet and gad jets are insecure and that the amount of digital information which a person generates with their help daily, in

as a result, constitutes its "digital footprint" in the digital space and cannot be removed.

Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that what is the fundamental difference between digital competence from information and communication competence is to integrate responsibility and motivation, which means the need for the subject to develop critical

logical thinking.

The purpose of this article is to identify the conditions development of digital competence of university students.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

clarify the term "digital competence";

- describe the levels of formation of digital competence;

- indicate the didactic forms of assessment formed

the importance of each level of digital competence;

- propose the conditions for the formation of a digital competence of university students.

Research results- In our understanding digital competence is the possession

methods of search, structuring, systematization analysis and critical evaluation of information using digital technologies and the global Internet for solutions for practical, educational and professional real tasks.

Based on the proposed interpretation of the digital competence, in its structure we single out the following levels of formation.

Levels of formation of digital competence are:

1) Gnoseological level - a necessary set knowledge to process information for the right purposes, communication, knowledge of terminology.

2) Motivational-value - is formed relatively solution to the use of digital technologies, ready-

ability to acquire new knowledge, attitude to in the formational field of the Internet as a tool, in including educational, develops critical thinking.

3) Activity-technological - acquisition skills of working with the global Internet with the necessary purpose, the use of information processing algorithms, mastering communication methods to solve practical problems tic, educational and professional tasks.

4) Effective-reflexive - assessment of one's own a high level of proficiency in digital technologies, self-mania as part of the digital environment.

At the epistemological level, theoretical theoretical knowledge about the methods of information processing, about structuring, coding and measurement of information

information, about ways of mastering software, knowledge of interdisciplinary

ties and opportunities for professional self improvement through digital technologies.

This level of development of digital competence characterized by the completeness and consistency of knowledge, which

which can be checked by the input diagnostic

sticky, testing, informational dictations, sedation, colloquium.

The creation of a POS provides the ability to design own knowledge necessary for adaptation

to the current labor market, the use of open online educational platforms and other resources global network Internet.

As a result of this research, it is possible to conclusion, that the construction of a PIC dictates the need to develop development of digital competence, since POS is initially formed spontaneously, but after a while, when the subject has a sufficiently large number

services and tools of the personal environment, raise the question of selection, ordering and systematization in their application, which requires digital skills and critical logical thinking, which means that the construction of a PIC allows to acquire knowledge and skills at all levels digital competence.

The development of a digital computer tentativeness and the design of the PIC are mutually conditioned processes: without a certain level digital competence impossible rational

construction of a PIC, but only with the help of a PIC is it possible development of a higher level of digital competence ness, because

this process is associated with the acquisition of activities verbal and personal experience.

The activity of the university is based on the network principle of learning using

digital educational platforms and optimizing small courses and teaching models of various universities.

The University sets as its task - by 2035 to create platform for providers of competencies, targeted these, competency profiles, allowing you to build personal development trajectory of the student.

Therefore, building a PIC is important a condition for the formation of digital competence of a specialist socialist as one of the necessary in the conditions of digital visions of society, economy and education.

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